

PECULIARITIES OF EXECUTION OF BUSINESS LETTERS IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK

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Modern science is increasingly focused on simplifying work through digitalization and electronic communication. Recently, the challenge of independently composing various letters and documents has garnered significant attention from linguists. Researchers have explored modern methods, highlighted key aspects, and examined various approaches to automating document management. The importance of using samples and templates when drafting statements, complaints, explanatory notes, reports, and other documents has been demonstrated. However, the systematic study of template usage in business correspondence remains largely unexplored [1].

An effective document management system is crucial in contemporary society. Every word and its form in a language are the result of a long historical development and the progress of human thought and emotion. Theoretically, many facets of business communication and document management are still insufficiently studied.

Business correspondence is a vital tool in today's world, facilitating effective communication between organizations and individuals.

The term "stylistics" comes from the word "style" (stylos): the ancient Greeks used this word to refer to a pointed stick for writing on wax tablets. Later, the word acquired the meaning "handwriting," and later "manner," "method," "features of speech" [2].

In the "Dictionary of the Russian Language" by S.I. Ozhegov (1990), the word STYLE and its related words are defined as follows:

1) A set of features, the similarity of expressive artistic techniques and means, which determine the unity of some direction in creativity. National style in painting. Architectural styles.

2) Method, a set of techniques of some work, activity, behavior. Management style. Swimming style. Style is the man. (prov.).

3) A set of techniques for using linguistic means to express certain ideas, thoughts in various conditions of speech practice, manner of writing. Styles of literary works. Pushkin's style. Journalistic style. In the style of someone/something, meaning in the manner of someone/something, similar to someone/something, corresponding to someone/something. To act in the style of one's teacher. || adj. stylistic (in 1st and 3rd meanings) and stylistic (in 3rd meaning). Stylistic device. Stylistic categories [Ozhegov 1990: 1789].

V.V. Vinogradov classifies styles based on three functions of language: communication (colloquial), information (business and scientific), influence (artistic and journalistic).

The official-business style serves the sphere of official-business relations that arise between state bodies, organizations, and private individuals in the course of their production, economic, and legal activities.

A norm is a set of the most suitable language means for serving society, formed as a result of selecting linguistic elements from among those that coexist, are newly formed, or are retrieved from the passive reserve of the past [Ozhegov 1984: 1502].

A norm determines human behavior in the process of communication, regulates the choice of linguistic means, and serves as a regulator of people's speech behavior [4].

Linguistic norms are the rules for using linguistic means during a certain period in the development of the literary language (rules of pronunciation, spelling, word usage, grammar). Speech norms are the rules that dictate how to speak in different situations and can vary depending on the region.

In business communication, it is important to be able to write personal and business letters, fill out forms, write autobiographies, and applications. The main goal is to convey information without errors and ambiguity.

Main characteristics of the official-business style:

1. Impersonality of vocabulary: Use of impersonal sentences.
2. Strict formality: Precision of expression without room for interpretation.
3. High regulation of expressions: Strictness in sentence construction.

External factors (extralinguistic):

1. Imperativeness: Use of infinitives and passive forms in the sense of directives.
2. Absence of variability and ambiguous interpretation: Absence of synonyms, repetitions, metaphors, and complex sentences.
3. Standardization: Set expressions (e.g., "file a claim," "render a verdict").
4. Objectivity: Impersonal constructions, priority of third-person forms.
5. Rationality: Constructions like "in connection with the refusal."

Directions of substyles of official-business literature and documentation:

1. Legal direction: Normative documents, laws, codes.
2. Diplomatic direction: Agreements, pacts, memorandums.
3. Business direction: Contracts, agreements, protocols.
4. Military direction: Orders, reports, requirements [5].

Genres of the official-business style: Charter, law, order, directive, contract, instruction, complaint, prescription, application, memorandum, power of attorney, business letters, and others.

Classification of business letters by purpose:

- Informational letters: Information letter, notification letter, reminder letter, announcement letter, advertising letter.
- Letters with requests or proposals: Request letter, inquiry letter, proposal letter, application letter, order letter, invitation letter.
- Letters with demands or complaints: Reminder letter, demand letter, complaint letter.

- Response letters: Acceptance letter, refusal letter.
- Letters with commitments, confirmations, guarantees: Guarantee letter, confirmation letter.
- Etiquette letters: Congratulatory letter.

Documents prepared in violation of standards may not have legal force. The letterhead is the organization's business card.

Methods of presenting the text:

- Chronological: sequence of events.
- Factual: main facts or points at the beginning of the letter, followed by details [6].

Rules of business etiquette:

- Politeness and respect for the business partner.
- Observance of formal subordination.
- Ability to express an opinion without offending the partner.
- Tolerance of other opinions.
- Honesty in business relations.
- Ability to conduct a debate correctly.

Structure of a business letter:

1. Heading
2. Salutation
3. Introductory paragraph
4. Main part
5. Conclusion
6. Signature.

Ancient cultural monuments and inscriptions found on various objects in Central Asia indicate that our ancestors adhered to a unique tradition of record-keeping from ancient times. In the Middle Ages, record-keeping acquired legal norms; secretariats and chanceries began to form in state institutions, and various forms of documents appeared [6].

The Uzbek language began to be used as an official business language during the rule of the Karakhanids. All documents prepared in the palace chanceries of Uzbek khans and emirs before the 20th century are distinguished by their unique style and content, specific order, and characteristic speech clichés.

During the Soviet era, although record-keeping in both Russian and Uzbek languages was legalized, the social status of the Uzbek language was low. With the independence of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek language, as the state language, has strengthened its position as the official language in which record-keeping is conducted.

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